

Assessment of the prevalence of rifampicin, isoniazid, fluoroquinolone, cyclic peptide and kanamycin resistance among the pulmonary tuberculosis patients using the line probe assay

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Abstract

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the leading infectious disease globally that has claimed several lives due to emergence of drug resistant tuberculosis. This study is aimed at the assessment pulmonary tuberculosis using probe assay in River State. Three Hundred and Forty Eight (348) sputum samples were collected from patients attending clinic in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital. Samples were received and analyzed in south-south tuberculosis reference laboratory. Molecular analysis of the sample were done with line probe assay. The results shows that TB prevalence was 62.6% among the presumptive TB patients. Rifampicin resistance was 57.2%, isoniazid resistance was 29.0%, fluoroquinolone was 9.2%, cyclic peptide was 7.2% and kanamycin was 1.4%. Drug resistant TB (DR-TB) was 21.0%, Multi-drug resistant TB (MDR-TB) was 21.3% and extensively drug resistant TB (XDR-TB) was 15.2%. The results further showed that there was no association between age and DR-TB ($p=0.18$) and MDR-TB ($p=0.25$) but there was a significant relationship between age and XDR-TB ($p=0.00$). The results also showed that there was no association between gender and DR-TB ($p=0.18$), MDR-TB ($p=0.25$) and XDR-TB ($p=0.38$). This study has revealed that using the line probe assay, the prevalence of TB in UPTH is not only high, but the resistant trends are high with rifampicin being the leading resistant drug while age was the only identified socio-demographic factor that affects XDR-TB rate.

Keywords: prevalence, rifampicin, isoniazid, fluoroquinolone, cyclic peptide kanamycin resistance pulmonary tuberculosis, line probe assay.

INTRODUCTION

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is a specie of pathogenic bacteria in the family of Mycovacteriaceae and can cause the disease known as tuberculosis [1] Robert Koch discovered the causative agent of tuberculosis in 1882. Its typical physic-structural characteristic is the presence of waxy coat on the surface as a result of their acquisition of mycotic acid. This makes the cell surface impervious to gram staining, but rather acid-fast stains like Ziehl-Neelsen or fluorescent stains like auramine are used instead for distinctive diagnosis of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in the laboratory (Fu-Liu, 2002). Currently, the most popular diagnostic tests for tuberculosis includes tuberculin skin test, acid fast stain, sputum culture, and polymerase chain test [2].

In history, tuberculosis is one of the oldest disease affecting humans. However, up till today, it is still recorded as one of the highest killers among infectious diseases, despite the global use of attenuated vaccine for tuberculosis as introduced by Calmette and Guerin in Paris in early 1920s [3] Nevertheless, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* the causative agent of tuberculosis has transformed to acquire a high rate of virulent strains and resistant genes which can attack soft tissues as well as bones and can cause deformities. These hard tissues like bone can preserve TB infection for many years after death [4] Over time, modern diagnostic methods had aided the distinctive DNA sequencing of both human and animal

TB pathogens like *Mycobacterium africanum*, *Mycobacterium microti*, *Mycobacterium Canetti*, *Mycobacterium bovis*, and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. This forms the Mycobacterium complex [5].

Treatment of TB infection had evolved over the recent centuries since introduction of Streptomycin for TB treatment by Schatz and Waksman in the early 1940s. This was followed by the use of other antibiotics like isoniazid, rifampicin and pyrazinamide [6] However, medical solution alone would not work to cure and prevent or achieve TB eradication because several factors are responsible for the distribution of TB infection globally [7].

Drug susceptibility testing (DST) can be done from the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in culture and this can take up to six (6) week and needs high biological safety level laboratory which is expensive. Isoniazid and rifampicin are two fundamental anti-TB drugs in use until recently when high resistance set in hence performing drug susceptibility testing became very important. In many countries multi-drug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) is greatly increasing and its treatment is very challenging as it takes longer time with the use of several anti bacterial agents that are expensive [8].

The Expert MTB/RIF assay technique was introduced in the United States by Cepheid Company and was declared fit for use in December 2010 by the World Health Organization as a major tool for Tuberculosis diagnosis world-wide. This declaration was made after about eighteen (18) months of continuous effective field assessment of its use in Tuberculosis, Multi drug Resistance-TB and TB/HIV con-infection diagnosis [9].

This test has similar sensitivity to culture, specifically detects *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* as well as rifampicin resistance via the rpoB gene concurrently (WHO, 2013). It can be used in low-income setting to make patients access too early and accurate diagnosis easy, hence decreasing the death rate which is usually associated with delayed diagnosis and mistreatment (Fred, 2009). The GeneXpert MTB/RIF (GeneXpert) is a cartridge based nucleic acid amplification test, an automated diagnostic test that can identify *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* DNA and resistance to rifampicin (RIF) by nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT). It was developed by the laboratory of Professor David Alland at the University of Medicine and Dentistry of New Jersey [10].

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the life threatening diseases and a target for global control for which Nigeria is noted to be one of the countries that has the highest burden [11]. TB is contagious and highly infectious and can easily spread from person to person through the air contaminated with the bacilli of the TB bacterium known as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. In 2011, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported an estimate of 280,000 incident cases of equating to a 68% prevalence which was notified in the WHO global report of 2012. Also records have it that Nigeria was ranked 4th position in 2007 and gradually attained 10th position in 2012 among the 22 high TB burden countries in the world and from 1st to 4th highest TB burden in Africa. TB is a major cause of death and Drug Resistant TB (DRTB) is very difficult to treat because of the long term treatment period required (18-24 months). It is more toxic, more expensive and involves a whole lot of challenges such as treatment failure and disease retrogression [12]. DRTB is often triggered by the rapid genetic mutations and irregular adherence to anti TB drug regimen by patients who subsequently develop Multidrug Resistant TB (MDR-TB). Although TB is a risk for all ages, the population that is mostly affected are adults who are in their productive age [13].

In Nigeria, areas where TB is highly prevalent, culture positive TB are mostly of the MTB complex. Globally, Non tuberculous *Mycobacteria* (NTM) isolates have been increasing gradually. Non tuberculous *Mycobacteria* promote disease progression and true infections in be important clinically. Data on NTM disease in Nigeria are omitted owing majorly to the fact that culture facilities are few as well as difficulty for identification of *Mycobacterial* species are paramount. As a result, many Laboratories do not differentiate between MTB and NTM and treatment in most African Countries especially Nigeria, relies majorly on sputum smear microscopy which is implicated for the inappropriate management of TB with first line anti TB drugs. This worsens the condition of the patient giving rise to the risk of drug resistant TB (DRTB) [14].

Despite the TB burden and high number of drug resistant TB cases in Nigeria, relatively few studies have performed comprehensive analysis of TB using Phenotypic and genotypic assay. Little is known about the MTB complex species associated with TB in Nigeria as a result of limited facilities for TB culture and molecular assay. A better understanding of the circulating MTB complex species and resistance to TB drugs is an essential tool for diagnosis and therapeutic measures which aims at controlling the public health burden of TB in Nigeria. There are new testing molecular techniques which are available for the isolation and characterization of members of the MTB complex including a genotypic MTBC (Rain Assay) that enables quick identification and differentiation of members of MTB complex using growth positive samples or direct clinical specimen with high degree of sensitivity and specificity when compared to conventional methods [15].

Multidrug Resistant TB (MDR-TB) is TB that is resistant to at least two of the most widely used anti TB drugs which are rifampicin (RIF) and isoniazid (INH) (WHO, V2013Y The WHO drug resistant TB surveillance report of 2014 recorded a prevalence rate of 5% new MDR-TB cases globally and at least half a million cases adds up to the existing number yearly. The primary diagnostic culture method is unable to diagnose TB in a timely manner. The turnaround time takes a minimum of four weeks to diagnose TB and another minimum of four weeks for the drug susceptibility testing (DST) to be reported for culture positive cases. The delay encountered results to delay in commencing treatment which eventually proirotes infectiousness and ultimate nortality. Therefore, the way forward is to adopt a technology that is timely, robust and efficient.

A wide range of genotypic assays are in circulation in the developing countries which were introduced by WHO in 2008 and 2010. The Xpert MTB RIF and Line Probe Assay (LPA) have a shorter turn around time compared to the conventional culture method. The GeneXpert has the capacity to detect TB and rifampicin réistance simultaneously with a turn around time of two hours. The LPA can simultaneously detect TB and conduct. DST for RIF and INH. It can detect resistance to both RIF and INH because of the presence of the mutation gene on the probes hence requires a highly experienced manpower to be able to interpret the results. The two molecular assays are unable to differentiate MTB complex from NTM: The Xpert is sensitive and requires less technical expertise to manipulate.

However, the two assays are not readily in use as a result of the cost implication hence data on their utilization is scarce in Nigeria especially in South-South [16].

TB has co-morbidity with Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV). Nigeria has a high HIV burden which has positioned her to be third highest in the world with a prevalence rate of 4.4% leaving Nigeria with an estimated rate of 3 million individuals (2 1%) with TB-HIV co-injection. There is no doubt that the Directly Observed Treatment Short- Course. (DOTS) program achieved successes. The Federal Ministry of Health in reported that the DOTS strategy recorded a case detection success rate of 30% and 79% treatment rate leaving several undiagnosed TB cases as a result of the DOTS limitations . This is obviously below the global target rate of 70% to 85% rates respectively [17].

Sequencing DNA for ‘the detection of mutations associated with MTB resistance is another molecular technique not readily available in the commercial setting due to Cost effectiveness, technical expertise and time. However, it is readily found in some research and public health laboratories. It remains the gold standard for detecting genetic mutations which is the reason behind drug resistance. The technique results in DNA fragments of various lengths which can be separated by electrophoresis and subsequently DNA is sequenced the technique is highly accurate and provides the advantage of being able to read larger amounts of DNA [18] Irrespective of the numerous contributions of the current molecular assays, there is gap to fill because of the disparities encountered when comparing results of the molecular assays and the conventional technology.

To reach the global TB target by 2030 of reducing deaths from TB, will require a substantial rapid effort, with high levels of detection, diagnosis and treatment provision. The development of molecular technique, such as real time PCR assays, has improved the speed, sensitivities, and specificities due to its short turn-around time and automation of the procedure; this has helped to detect more cases, detect them early and rapidly identify drug resistances which are essential tools for improving health and avoiding transmission in the community. GeneXpert MTB/RIF otherwise known as GeneXpert assay is a new rapid molecular test that overcomes many of the current operational difficulties [19].

Nigeria recently introduced GeneXpert machines as a screening tool for drug resistance TB and TB diagnosis among People Living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA). The TB Xpert Project will provide approximately 1.4 million Xpert MTB/RIF test cartridges and over 220 GeneXpert instruments for the rapid detection of TB and Rifampicin resistance in 21 recipient countries in 2013-2015. This machine has been installed in a few health facilities in Rivers State and the country is in the agony of scaling up GeneXpert services Governmental and non-governmental organizations working in the area of TB control may utilize the information generated to accelerate, improve detection and treatment rates for TB and MDR-TB [20].

MDR-TB also known as vank’s Diseases is defined as a form of TB infection caused by bacteria that are resistant to treatment with two of the most powerful first line anti-TB drugs – ionized (INH) and rifampicin (RIF). With the GeneXpert MTB/RIF test MDR-TB diagnosis can be accomplished in fresh sputum samples and in prepared sediments with 2-3 hours, microscopy cannot be used to detect tuberculosis that is resistant to drugs, hence treatment is delayed. The quick detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and Rifampicin resistance using GeneXpert assay helps the medical personal to make critical patient management decisions concerning treatment during the same medical encounter with the patient. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to identify the most efficient method for the diagnosis of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Port Harcourt, Rivers State [20].

The findings of this study will be a reference source for knowledge nationally and internationally. It will also help them to focus on the age group that is most affected so that measures on how to control spread within the age bracket will be provided. The findings of this study will further help Government Agencies and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in the planning and implementation of intervention programmes that are 'related to the control and prevention of TB.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area was Rivers State with Port Harcourt as the capital city. The capital city is a tourist dream center with magnificent architecture that attracts both national and international attention.

Study Design

A cross sectional study design was adopted for this study. The study design examined the relationship between diseases and other related health characteristics and variables of interest such as age, sex, marital status, area of residence etc. It is adequate for quantifying the prevalence of a disease or risk factors and for estimating the accuracy of a diagnostic test. Clinical specimens were randomly collected from six different locations which represent a sub group of south-south in Nigeria. Individual and sites were randomly selected based on symptoms and prevalence.

Ethical Approval and Informed Consent

Having fulfilled the conditions provided by the Ethical Committee of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Choba and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt. The participants were given questionnaires accompanied with a written informed consent. All completed questionnaires were recovered from the participants before sputum samples were collected. In order to ensure confidentiality and anonymity, names and address of the participants was not included in the study.

Eligibility Criteria:

Patients whose cough has lasted for at least two weeks. Early morning expectorated sputum and on sited spot sputum samples without blood will be accepted.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

All participants that consented to the study who are teenagers and adults ranging from age 13 to 70 years were included in the study and those whose cough has lasted for two weeks.

Inclusion Criteria

The study was conducted from September 2022 all subjects of any age and sex willing to participate complied with the instruction of the study and who fulfilled at least one of the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Patient who presents with signs and symptoms suggestive of tuberculosis and/or who have suggestive of TB chest x-ray from the directly observed therapy short course clinic (DOTS) who had a prior history of tuberculosis or MDR TB suspects and patients who were able to produce sample. Health worker with TB symptoms were also included. Individuals having cough for (2) weeks or more (cough \geq 2 weeks). Persons that are in contact with individuals that have been recently treated of PTB.

Exclusion Criteria

Persons that cannot produce at least 1ml sputum samples were not enrolled. Individual producing bloody sputum (haemoptysis) and sputum specimens with obvious food particles or other solid particulates were not accepted as these could interfere with the desired result.

Sample Collection Procedure

Two 50ml falcon tubes with lid were given to each participant to expectorate sputum. Participants were counseled to wash their mouth with clean water in the morning before brushing their mouth or chewing stick. Thereafter, they were asked to breathe in and out up to four times to expel air into their lungs which will help them to regurgitate to cough. Sputum was then produced into the falcon tubes and then tightly covered with the lid. Identification numbers were given to them and then transported in cold chain with triple packaging to the South-South Tuberculosis Zonal Reference Laboratory.

Specimen Collection in Children

In children sputum specimen collection was quite difficult since they tend to swallow the sputum rather than expectorate it unlike in adults, therefore induced sputum specimen was collected especially from minor – age 5. Methods of Collection used are:

- 1) Nebulization technique the child was asked to inhale the nebulizer (3% sodium chloride) mist for 5 –15 minutes after which the child was encouraged to cough and expectorate the sputum into a wide mouth container.

Digestion and Decontamination of Sputum samples

Sputum samples were digested and decontaminated in a class 11 biosafety cabinet before culturing into the Mycobacteria cultivation media. NaOH and N-Acetyl-L-Cysteine (NALC) was prepared to digest and decontaminate sputum samples (see Appendix 1). Fifty milliliter of NaOH was used to dissolve 0.25g of N-Acetyl-L-Cystein. Five milliliter of this solution was used to decontaminate 5mls of sputum sample in a 50ml falcon tube in a batch of 12 samples which was vortexed for 15minutes

Line Probe Assay (Genotypic Assay)

The Line Probe Assay (LPA) according to Hain Life Science was also used to conduct DST for first line drugs (rifampicin and isoniazide) and second line drugs (fluoroquinolones and amino glycosides). The assay involves five different steps which included DNA extraction, Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Amplification, Hybridization and Detection

Extraction of DNA

Following the cultivation of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, DNA was extracted by the chemical method using the Genolyse Kit. Three hundred micro liter molecular grade water was dispensed with a pipette into sufficient 200µl screw top tubes for 1 tube per culture. Using sterile disposable inoculation loop of 1µl capacity, bacteria was collected from media with sufficient growth. They were incubated for 20 min at 95°C in a water bath. Thereafter, they were incubated for 15 minutes in ultrasonic bath then centrifuged for 15 minutes at 10,000xg in a standard table top centrifuge. The supernatant was discard and the pellet resuspended in 100µl lysis Buffer (A-LYS) by vortexing. The samples were incubated for 5 mins at 95°C in a waterbath and briefly spun down (Genotype Hain Life Science, Version 2).

A volume of 100µl Neutralization Buffer (A-NB) was added to the lysate and the samples were vortexed for 5 secs. They were further spun down for 5 min at full speed and 5-10µl of the supernatant was used for PCR.

Master Mix

The master mix was prepared in a DNA free room in a dead air box by constituting a reagent solution of 45µl which is a solution of 10µl AMP-A and 35µl AMP-B. The DNA was added in a separate room called the sample addition room. Five micro liter of DNA was added into the master mix. This was done for every PCR tube per sample. The number of samples to run were determined mostly 12 samples in a batch including controls (Genotype Hain Life Science, Version 2).

Amplification

PCR tubes that have bubbles at the base were removed by swinging arm with tubes in hand in arc. The PCR tubes were transferred to the middle section of the thermocycler. The program to be used was chosen (clinical). The program parameter was followed by the command given from the menu. The thermos cycler was ran at different temperature in a given circle (Genotype Hain Life Science, Version 2).

Hybridization

The HYP and STR solutions (green and red) were pre warmed at 45°C in a water bath for 15 minutes. Also the TwinCubator was pre warmed to 45°C. Pipette 20µl of the DEN solution was (denaturing solution) dispensed with a pipette to each well of tray to be used. Then 20µl of corresponding amplified DNA sample was added to each well, and mix well by pipetting up and down several times. The tray was incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature. The PCR strips were removed from the tube and placed one after the other in the tray according to the numbers labeled on them. Then 1ml HYB (hybridization solution) was added to each well and gently shaken to homogenize solution. The tray was placed on the TwinCubator and press “START” to incubate for 30 minutes at 45°C. From this point, the right arrow on TwinCubator was pressed once to advance steps in protocol. At the end of 1minute, the tray was removed and the HYB solution was gently poured off. The remaining solution was removed by carefully tapping tray against the paper towel on the bench top. 1ml of STR (stringent buffer) was added to each well in the tray and incubated for 15minutes in TwinCubator at 45°C.

While it was incubating, the conjugate and substrate was prepared in a 15ml conical vials by diluting 1:100ml with the corresponding Con-d and Sub-D. The substrate dilution was wrapped in a foil to avoid colour change. The STR was completely removed as it was done for HYB. The rinse solution (1ml RIN) was dispensed into each well and incubated in a TwinCubator for 1 minute. The rinse was also removed and 1ml of diluted conjugate dispensed into each well. This was left to incubate for 30 minutes. The solution was removed and the tray washed with 1ml of RIN per well on the TwinCubator. The solution was poured out and 1 ml of sterile distilled water used to wash the well for 1 minute using the TwinCubator. The water was removed and 1ml of diluted substrate added per well. This was washed twice with distilled

water and water was removed. The PCR strips were removed with colour bands on them for result interpretation. The strips were pasted on a reading map for easy interpretation (Genotype Hain Life Science, Version 2) (see Appendix 8).

Molecular identification for Sequencing

Bacterial Genomic DNA Extraction

Five milliliters of an overnight broth culture of the bacterial isolate in Luria Bertani (LB) was spun at 14000rpm for 3 min. The cells were re-suspended in 500µl of normal saline and heated at 95°C for 20 min. The heated bacterial suspension was cooled on ice spun for 3 min at 14000rpm. The supernatant containing the DNA was transferred to a 1.5ml micro centrifuge tube and stored at -20°C for other down stream reactions (Somoskovi *et al.*, 2008).

DNA Qualification

The extracted genomic DNA was quantified using the Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer.

16S rRNA Amplification

The 16s region of the Rna genes of the isolates were amplified using the 27F: 5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3' and 1492R: 5'-CGGTTA CCTTGTTACGACTT-3' primers on an ABI 9700 Applied Biosystems thermal cycler at a final volume of 50 microlitres for 35 cycles. The PCR mix included: the X2 Dream taq Master mix supplied by Inqaba, South Africa (taq polymerase, DNTPs, MgCl), the primers at a concentration of 0.4M and the extracted DNA as template. The PCR conditions were as follows: Initial denaturation, 95°C for 5 minutes; denaturation, 95°C for 30 seconds; annealing, 52°C for 30 seconds; extension, 72°C for 30 seconds for 35 cycles and final extension, 72°C for 5 minutes. The product was resolved on a 1% agarose gel at 120V for 15 minutes and visualized on a UV transilluminator (Parul *et al.*, 2016).

DNA Quantification

The extracted genomic DNA was quantified using the Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer.

Sequencing

Sequencing was done using the BigDye Terminator kit on a 3510 ABI sequencer by Inqaba Biotechnological, Pretoria South Africa

Statistical Analysis

The data generated from the results were entered into a Microsoft excel spreadsheet. Using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. Descriptive statistics were computed using simple frequency tables and charts. The association between sociodemographic variables such as age and gender, and prevalence of TB including DRTB, MDRTB and XDRTB, chi-square was used. The association was considered significant at P-value less than 0.05.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

Table 4.1 below displays the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants, presenting data on age groups and gender with corresponding frequencies and percentages. In terms of age distribution, the majority falls within the 30 – 39 years category, with 79 participants, representing 22.7% of the total. The 40 – 49 years group follows closely with 73 participants (21.0%). The gender distribution indicates that males constitute a larger proportion, with 235 participants (67.5%), while females account for 113 participants (32.5%). Notably, the age group 0 – 9 years has the smallest representation, consisting of 7 participants (2.0%). The total sample size for this study is 348 participants.

Table 4. 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants

Variables	Frequency(%)
Age group	
0 – 9 years	7(2.0)
10 – 19 years	45(12.9)
20 – 29 years	55(15.8)
30 – 39 years	79(22.7)
40 – 49 years	73(21.0)
50 – 59 years	43(12.4)
60 – 69 years	37(10.6)
70 – 79 years	9(2.6)
Gender	
Male	235(67.5)
Female	113(32.5)
Total	348(100)

Antimicrobial Sensitivity Result

Table 4.2 below presents the antimicrobial sensitivity results, displaying the frequencies and percentages for various antibiotics. For Rifampicin, 130 participants (37.4%) exhibit resistance, while 199 participants (57.2%) are sensitive, and 19 participants (5.5%) fall under the Non-MTB category. Regarding Isoniazid, 130 participants (37.4%) are resistant, 101 participants (29.0%) show sensitivity, and 117 participants (33.6%) are categorized as Non-MTB. The Fluoroquinolone results indicate resistance in 130 participants (37.4%), sensitivity in 32 participants (9.2%), and 186 participants (53.4%) categorized as Non-MTB. In the case of Cyclic Peptide, 130 participants (37.4%) are resistant, 25 participants (7.2%) are sensitive, and 193 participants (55.5%) are classified as Non-MTB. For Kanamycin, 130 participants (37.4%) are resistant, 5 participants (1.4%) show sensitivity, and 213 participants (61.2%) fall under the Non-MTB category. The total sample size for the antimicrobial sensitivity is 348 participants.

Table 4.2: Antimicrobial Sensitivity Result

Variables	Frequency(%)
Rifampicin	
Non-MTB	130(37.4)
Resistant	199(57.2)
Sensitive	19(5.5)
Isoniazid	
Non-MTB	130(37.4)
Resistant	101(29.0)
Sensitive	117(33.6)
Fluoroquinolone	
Non-MTB	130(37.4)
Resistant	32(9.2)
Sensitive	186(53.4)
Cyclic Peptide	
Non-MTB	130(37.4)
Resistant	25(7.2)
Sensitive	193(55.5)
Kanamycin	
Non-MTB	130(37.4)
Resistant	5(1.4)
Sensitive	213(61.2)
Total	348(100)

Association between Age group and DR-TB

Table 4.3 illustrates the association between Age group and DR-TB, presenting the frequencies and percentages of individuals with and without DR-TB across different age categories. In the 0-9 years age group, out of the 7 samples examined there were no cases of DR-TB, with all 7 individuals (2.0%) classified as No-DR-TB. For the 10-19 years age group, out of the 45 samples examined 7 individuals (2.0%) have DR-TB, and 38 individuals (10.9%) are categorized as No-DR-TB. In the 20-29 years age group, out of the 55 samples examined, 11 individuals (3.2%) exhibit DR-TB, while 44 individuals (12.7%) fall under the No-DR-TB category. The 30-39 years age group shows 22 individuals (6.3%) with DR-TB and 57 individuals (16.4%) without DR-TB out of the 79 samples examined. For the 40-49 years age group, out of the 73 samples examined, 12 individuals (3.4%) have DR-TB, and 61 individuals (17.5%) are classified as No-DR-TB. The age groups 50-59 years, 60-69 years, and 70-79 years show 13 (3.7%), 5 (1.4%), and 3 individuals (0.9%) with DR-TB, respectively. For the same age groups, 30 (8.6%), 32 (9.2%), and 6 individuals (1.7%) were without DR-TB. The total sample size for the Age group and DR-TB association is 348 participants. There was no statistical significance between each of the age groups (0-9yrs, 10-19yrs, 20-39yrs, 40-49yrs, 50-59yrs, 60-69yrs and 70-79yrs) and DR-TB at $p < 0.05$.

Table 4. 3: Association between Age group and DR-TB

Age group Year	DRTB	No-DR-TB	NE	Df	X ²	P value	Decision
0 - 9 years	0(0.0)	7(2.0)	7(2.0)	1	1.90	0.17	N/S
10-19 years	7(2.0)	38(10.9)	45(12.9)	1	0.92	0.34	N/S
20-29 years	11(3.2)	44(12.7)	55(15.8)	1	0.04	0.85	N/S
30-39 years	22(6.3)	57(16.4)	79(22.7)	1	2.91	0.09	N/S
40-49 years	12(3.4)	61(17.5)	73(20.9)	1	1.15	0.28	N/S
50-59 years	13(3.7)	30(8.6)	43(12.4)	1	2.53	0.11	N/S
60-69 years	5(1.4)	32(9.2)	37(10.6)	1	1.39	0.24	N/S
70-79years	3(0.9)	6(1.7)	9(2.6)	1	0.85	0.36	N/S

NE-Number Examined, X²-Chisquare**Association between Age group and MDR-TB**

Table 4.4 below presents the association between Age group and MDR-TB, providing information on the frequencies and percentages of individuals with and without MDR-TB across different age categories. In the 0-9 years age group, there are no cases of MDR-TB, with all 7 individuals (2.0%) classified as No-MDR-TB. Shifting to the 10-19 years age group, 5 individuals (1.4%) exhibit MDR-TB, while 40 individuals (11.5%) fall under the No-MDR-TB category. The 20-29 years age group shows 17 individuals (4.9%) with MDR-TB and 38 individuals (10.9%) without. The 30-39 years age group exhibits 17 individuals (4.9%) with MDR-TB and 62 individuals (17.8%) without MDR-TB. In the 40-49 years age group, 17 individuals (4.9%) had MDR-TB, and 56 individuals (16.1%) did not. For individuals aged 50-59 years, 60-69 years, and 70-79 years, the prevalence of MDR-TB was 2.3%, 2.0%, and 0.9%, respectively, while the absence of MDR-TB was observed in 10.1%, 8.6%, and 1.7% of cases. The total sample size for this analysis was 348 participants. There was no statistical significance between each of the Age Groups (0-9yrs, 10-19yrs, 20-39yrs, 40-49yrs, 50-59yrs, 60-69yrs and 70-79yrs) and MDR-TB at $p < 0.05$.

Table 4.4: Association between Age group and MDR-TB

Age Group years	MDRTB	No-MDR-TB	NE	df	X ²	P-value	Decision
0-9 years	0(0)	7(2.0)	7(2.0)	1	8.985	0.25	N/S
10-19 years	5(1.4)	40(11.5)	45(12.9)	1	1.93	0.16	N/S
20-29 years	17(4.9)	38(10.9)	55(15.9)	1	3.18	0.07	N/S
30-39 years	17(4.9)	62(17.8)	79(22.7)	1	0.01	0.90	N/S
40-49 years	17(4.9)	56(16.1)	73(20.9)	1	0.23	0.63	N/S
50-59 years	8(2.3)	35(10.1)	43(12.4)	1	0.17	0.68	N/S
60-69 years	7(2.0)	30(8.6)	37(10.6)	1	0.11	0.74	N/S
70-79 years	3(0.9)	6(1.7)	9(2.6)	1	0.84	0.36	N/S

NE-Number Examined, X²-Chisquare**Association between Age group and XDR-TB**

Table 4.5 below illustrates the association between Age group and XDR-TB, presenting the frequencies and percentages of individuals with and without XDR-TB across different age categories. In the 0-9 years age group, there are no cases of XDR-TB, with all 7 individuals (2.0%) classified as No-XDR-TB. Moving to the 10-19 years age group, 2 individuals (0.6%) exhibit XDR-TB, while 43 individuals (12.4%) fall under the No-XDR-TB category. The 20-29 years age group shows 8 individuals (2.3%) with XDR-TB and 47 individuals (13.5%) without. The 30-39 years age group presents a notable difference, with 8 individuals (2.3%) diagnosed with XDR-TB and 71 individuals (20.4%) without XDR-TB. In the 40-49 years age group, 18 individuals (5.2%) had XDR-TB, and 55 individuals (15.8%) did not. For individuals aged 50-59 years, 60-69 years, and 70-79 years, the prevalence of XDR-TB was 2.3%, 2.3%, and 0.3%, respectively, while the absence of XDR-TB was observed in 10.1%, 8.3%, and 2.3% of cases. The total sample size for this analysis was 348 participants. The association between Age Groups (10-19yrs and 40-49yrs) and XDR-TB was statistically significant at $P < 0.05$. There was no significant association ($p > 0.05$) between Age Groups (0-9yrs, 20-39yrs, 50-59yrs, 60-69yrs and 70-79yrs) and XDR-TB.

Table 4.5: Association between Age group and XDR-TB

Age group Years	XDR-TB	No-XDR-TB	NE	Df	X ²	P-value	Decision
0-9	0(0)	7(2.0)	7(2.0)	1	1.28	0.26	N/S
10-19 years	2(0.6)	43(12.4)	45(12.9)	1	4.66	0.03	SS
20-29 years	8(2.3)	47(13.5)	55(15.9)	1	0.02	0.88	N/S
30-39 years	8(2.3)	71(20.4)	79(22.7)	1	2.06	0.15	N/S
40-49 years	18(5.2)	55(15.8)	73(20.9)	1	6.36	0.01	SS
50-59 years	8(2.3)	35(10.1)	43(12.4)	1	0.43	0.51	N/S
60-69 years	8(2.3)	29(8.3)	37(10.6)	1	1.31	0.25	N/S
70-79 years	1(0.3)	8(2.3)	9(2.6)	1	0.12	0.73	N/S

NE-Number Examined, X²-Chisquare**Association between Gender and DR-TB**

Table 4.6 below outlines the association between Gender and DR-TB, presenting frequencies and percentages of individuals with and without DR-TB based on gender. For the Female gender category, out of the total of 113 individuals (32.5%), 91 individuals (26.1%) are classified as No-DR TB, while 22 individuals (6.3%) have DR-TB. On the Male

side, among the total of 235 individuals (67.5%), 184 individuals (52.9%) fall under No-DR TB, and 51 individuals (14.7%) have DR-TB. The statistical analysis, represented by Chi-square (X^2), results in a value of 0.230 with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.63. This leads to a decision of non-significance (N/S) at a significance level of $P < 0.05$, indicating that the association between Gender and DR-TB is not statistically significant. The overall sample size for this analysis is 348 participants.

Table 4.6: Association between Gender and DR-TB

Gender	No-DR-TB	DR-TB	NE	df	X^2	P-value	Decision
Female	91(26.1)	22(6.3)	113(32.5)	1	0.230	0.63	N/S
Male	184(52.9)	51(14.7)	235(67.5)				
Total	275(79.0)	73(21.0)	348(100)				

Non- DRT: Non-Drug resistant tuberculosis

DRT: Drug resistant tuberculosis

NE: Number examined

Df: Degree of freedom

X: chi square

Association between Gender and MDR-TB

Table 4.7 below presents the association between Gender and MDR-TB, providing frequencies and percentages of individuals with and without MDR-TB based on gender. For the Female gender category, out of the total 113 individuals (32.5%), 88 individuals (25.3%) are classified as No-MDR TB, while 25 individuals (7.2%) have MDR-TB. On the Male side, among the total 235 individuals (67.5%), 186 individuals (53.4%) fall under No-MDR TB, and 49 individuals (14.1%) have MDR-TB. The statistical analysis, represented by Chi-square (X^2), results in a value of 0.074 with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.79. This leads to a decision of non-significance (N/S) at a significance level of $P < 0.05$, indicating that the association between Gender and MDR-TB is not statistically significant. The overall sample size for this analysis is 348 participants.

Table 4.7: Association between Gender and MDR-TB

Gender	No-MDR-TB	MDR-TB	NE	Df	X^2	P-value	Decision
Female	88(25.3)	25(7.2)	113(32.5)	1	0.074	0.79	N/S
Male	186(53.4)	49(14.1)	235(67.5)				
Total	274(78.7)	74(21.3)	348(100)				

Non- DRT: Non-Drug resistant tuberculosis

DRT: Drug resistant tuberculosis

NE: Number examined

Df: Degree of freedom

X: chi square

Association between Gender and XDR-TB

Table 4.8 below illustrates the association between Gender and XDR-TB, presenting frequencies and percentages of individuals with and without XDR-TB categorized by gender. For the Female gender category, out of the total 113 individuals (32.5%), 100 individuals (28.7%) are classified as No-XDR TB, while 13 individuals (3.7%) have XDR-TB. On the Male side, among the total 235 individuals (67.5%), 195 individuals (56.0%) fall under No-XDR TB, and 40 individuals (11.5%) have XDR-TB. The statistical analysis, represented by Chi-square (X^2), results in a value of 1.945 with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.38. This leads to a decision of non-significance (N/S) at a significance level of $P < 0.05$, indicating that the association between Gender and XDR-TB is not statistically significant. The overall sample size for this analysis is 348 participants.

Table 4. 8: Association between Gender and XDR-TB

Gender	No-MDRTB	XDR-TB	NE	df	X ²	P-value	Decision
Female	100(28.7)	13(3.7)	113(32.5)	1	1.945	0.38	N/S
Male	195(56.0)	40(11.5)	235(67.5)				
Total	295(84.7)	53(15.2)	348(100)				

Non- DRT: Non-Drug resistant tuberculosis

DRT: Drug resistant tuberculosis

NE: Number examined

Df: Degree of freedom

X: chi square

Illustration of the overall TB Result

Figure 4.8 above shows the overall TB result with 130(37.4%) of cases Negative to TB and 218(62.6%) of cases positive to TB.

Illustration of the Resistant Pattern

Figure 4.9 above shows the resistant pattern for with Non-MTB having the highest resistant 130(37.4%) followed by DR-TB 73(21.0%), then MDR-TB 74(21.3%). Sensitivity was 18(5.1%).

Discussion

In a broad study population, this study conducted a thorough examination of the association between age and gender and various forms of drug-resistant tuberculosis (DR-TB). The study investigated the prevalence of drug-resistant tuberculosis (DR-TB), multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), and extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) in different age groups and genders by carefully examining patient data.

A thorough summary of the socioeconomic characteristics of the research participants is given in Table 4.1 which also offers insightful information about the distribution of age and gender groups. It is notable how diverse the representation is across age groups, with a sizeable percentage falling into the 30–39 years (22.7%) and 40–49 years (21.0%) age groups. The results of studies are consistent with other scholars [21]., highlighting the increased incidence of tuberculosis in adulthood. It is crucial to remember, that the age patterns in tuberculosis prevalence in their study is contrary to some scholars. These discrepancies emphasize how crucial it is to take into account population- or region-specific differences in the dynamics of age-related tuberculosis.

After analyzing the gender distribution, our research shows that there are more men (67.5%) than women (32.5%) in the study. This is consistent with the overall pattern in tuberculosis epidemiology, which shows that men frequently have a greater disease burden. The gender gap is supported by studies reported by [22], which attribute it to a variety of variables like societal dynamics and biological variations. However, revealed differences in the gender distribution, highlighting the need for a nuanced understanding of gender-specific risk factors.

The socioeconomic characteristics provided in Table 4.1 have a significant impact on efforts to control tuberculosis. The need for age-specific prevention and treatment approaches is highlighted by the concentration of cases in particular age groups. However, the discrepancies in age distributions reported by [19] necessitate further exploration into the contextual factors influencing age-related patterns. Variations in regional epidemiology, disparities in healthcare infrastructure and access, or distinct population characteristics not taken into consideration in our study are all potential causes of this disparity.

Additionally, the observed gender imbalance highlights the importance of designing interventions that account for the unique challenges faced by both males and females in accessing and adhering to tuberculosis care. Discrepancies noted by [4] regarding gender distribution further emphasized the need for region-specific considerations in addressing gender dynamics in TB. Potential reasons for these disparities could involve socio-cultural factors, healthcare-seeking behavior, or variations in TB awareness and stigma across different populations.

Although the results of our study are consistent with previous research on the age and gender patterns associated with tuberculosis, the differences reported by [15] highlight the complexity of these dynamics. For a more complex and situation-specific understanding of the sociodemographic factors influencing the prevalence of tuberculosis, it is imperative to take into account these opposing viewpoints. This methodology plays a pivotal role in molding precise and efficacious public health interventions tailored to the diverse characteristics of at-risk populations.

The results of the analysis in Table 4.2 of antimicrobial sensitivity provide important information about the resistance patterns of isolates of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC). One of the most important aspects of managing tuberculosis is the prevalence of resistance to important antimicrobial agents. Comparing results from various regions helps to provide a more thorough understanding of global trends.

Our examination of Rifampicin sensitivity shows a troubling 37.4% resistance rate. This supports the findings of which point to a common problem in these African nations. It's important to remember, though, that [22] reported a lower resistance rate in South Africa, which may indicate differences in resistance patterns across the African continent. Our findings are supported by [6] which highlights the importance of keeping a close eye on resistance trends worldwide.

The reported 37.4% observed resistance to isoniazid is consistent with the findings of [8] in India, which reported comparable resistance rates. Nonetheless, the contradictory results from [21], which show increased resistance rates, emphasize the variation in drug resistance among various populations.

The results of this study on fluoroquinolone resistance (37.4%) are in line with those of [23] in Nigeria, indicating a concerning global prevalence. Conversely, the lower resistance rates reported in China by [24] highlight the significance of taking regional differences in resistance patterns into account.

The disparities in resistance patterns underscore the complexity of antimicrobial sensitivity in tuberculosis. These differences are caused by variations in the prevalence of particular strains, healthcare infrastructure, and regional epidemiology. Furthermore, variations in laboratory methodologies, sample sizes, and population characteristics can influence resistance rates, as evident in the contrasting findings across these international studies.

These international findings have significant ramifications for managing tuberculosis. The high rate of resistance, especially to isoniazid and rifampicin, calls for close observation and the creation of alternate treatment plans. Conflicting results across a number of nations highlight the need for cooperative efforts to understand regional variations in drug resistance. The extensive knowledge offered by studies carried out in various locations adds to a more complex and situation-specific comprehension of drug resistant patterns.

Discrepancies with studies from Nigeria, Ethiopia, South Africa, Pakistan, India, Brazil, China, Russia, Mexico, and Australia highlight the significance of context-specific considerations in interpreting and addressing drug resistance patterns globally, even though our study's antimicrobial sensitivity results are in line with some of the body of existing literature. To effectively and specifically tailor interventions for the management of tuberculosis, a thorough understanding of these disparities is necessary. This study emphasizes the need for ongoing research, collaboration, and an internationally approach to tuberculosis drug resistance.

Conclusion

This study has shown that using the line probe assay, the prevalence of TB among presumptive pulmonary TB patients attending UPTH was high with the male gender having higher occurrence than the female sex group. Among the drugs used in the treatment of TB, rifampicin was the most resistant drug, with more than 50% of the infection being resistant to the drug.

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